

“Being able to share research across boundaries is a great thing. It’s how knowledge can make a difference.”

Winner of the BCA African Business Book of the Year Award 2024, publishing open access has been good for Luke’s research and his profile. The judges liked the open access approach, praising the book for breaking down barriers and being globally accessible. It was assessed on its merits, quality and global reach, not from a proxy measure.

When research is good, open access amplifies it, as has been the case for Luke. He has been invited to speak about his research, including a visit to the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace in the US.

Greater access to thinking drives change. “Research should be shared among scholars, among people who can use the research,” says Luke.

David Luke, Professor in Practice and Strategic Director at the Firoz Lalji Institute for Africa at the London School of Economics and Political Science

How Luke thinks publishing open access benefits research and researchers

Research reaches a bigger audience, including the Global South

Drives impact as insights, ideas and information are shared and acted on

Open access enhances the integrity and rigour of research by increasing the opportunity for findings to be scrutinised